

Multifunctional Composites for Energy Harvesting

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1 Introduction

To date, composite materials have been used in many fields, including biology, engineering, aerospace, sports, and energy harvesting, because of the excellent performances obtained from the combination of matrices and fillers. Many researchers have combined fillers and matrices to create materials with new functional properties, and improve the performance of composites. Although pure lead zirconate titanate (PZT) ceramics show strong piezoelectric effects, the brittleness of these materials has limited their applications. However, very few composites with both piezoelectric and shape memory effects have been reported.

The aims :

1. Try to improve the flexibility of PZT composites
2. Try to use electrospinning to prepare a multifunctional flexible nanofiber composite with PZT particles and shape memory polymers

2 Methods

To modify the PZT fillers, a 1 g portion of the PZT particles were refluxed in a mixture of 3 g of acetone and 0.05 g of silane coupling agent. This mixture was then heated at 55 °C for 3 h with vigorous mixing by the ultrasonic device. Next, the mixture was dried in a vacuum desiccator at 70 °C for 12 h to completely remove the acetone solution.

The PZT particles were poured into a mixed solution of THF/DMF, and dispersed with an ultrasonic. Then THF was evaporated at room temperature until the ratio of shape memory polyurethane(SMPU) to solvent was 1:7.

The PZT/SMPU nanofibers were prepared by an electrospinning method. A voltage of 15 kV was applied over the spinneret at a distance of 11 cm from the collector. The syringe was compressed at 1.69 mL/min, the speed of the collector was 5 m/min, and the spinneret had a swing speed of 3 cm/min.

The Pb-Pt alloy was magnetron sputtered on the surface of the prepared fiber film samples to form an interdigitated electrode shape. Then, the samples were polarized at 10 kV/mm in 80 °C silicone oil for 2 h.

All the samples were cut into rectangles (10 mm length and 2 mm width). To obtain accurate results, all samples were stretched under the same stress. To ensure vertical sample placement, the samples were heated to 71 °C prior to the stretching cycle, and applied with an initial stress of 0.012 MPa to maintain their straight alignment.

These steps constituted one cycle, and each sample was subjected to three cycles.

The one end of sample is fixed and the other free, with the free-end contacting the vibration exciter. The sinusoidal signal and frequency were adjusted via a signal generator. The vibrational frequency was ranged from 600 to 2000 Hz, and the acceleration of the vibration was controlled by the exciter. An accelerometer was mounted on the top of the vibration exciter. The acceleration was varied by adjusting the exciting current of the signal amplifier. The output voltages of the piezoelectric materials were also measured with the oscilloscope.

3 Results

Shape recovery performance

Fig. 3 Shape memory performance of pristine SMPU and PZT/SMPU nanofibers. (a) Comparison of strain of different samples over three cycles, (b) Image of sample recovering, (c) Shape memory performances of pristine SMPU and PZT / SMPU nanofibers.

Although the shape memory properties of the PZT/SMPU nanofibers decreased as the content of PZT particles increased, the shape recovery performance of the PZT 80%-M remained at 84.8% in the first cycle. In the second and third cycles of the shape recovery test, the recovery rates of the modified PZT/SMPU nanofibers were greater than 94%.

Fig. 4 Schematic diagram of PZT/SMPU nanofibers deforming and adhering to the surfaces of complex structures for energy harvesting.

Energy harvesting performance

Fig. 5 Piezoelectric performance of PZT/SMPU nanofibers. (a) Output voltages of modified PZT/SMPU nanofibers at various acceleration and 800 Hz. (b) PZT 80%-M (c) PZT 70%-M (d) PZT 60%-M (e) Output voltages of modified PZT/SMPU nanofibers at various frequencies and acceleration of 470 mm/s² (f) PZT 80%-M, (g) PZT 70%-M, and (h) PZT 60%-M.

The output voltages of the piezoelectric materials increased as the acceleration was increased. Under continuous sinusoidal vibration (from 600 to 2000 Hz), the output voltages of the modified nanofibers first increased

4 Conclusions

We prepare PZT/SMPU nanofibers, which have both piezoelectric and shape memory properties. The amount of aggregation of the PZT fillers in SMPU matrices are reduced by modification of the PZT particles with a silane coupler agent. The mechanical properties of the modified nanofibers improved, including the break strains (by at least 5.03%), yield stresses (by at least 5.47%) and tensile strengths (by at least 9.36%).

The shape recovery rates of the PZT/SMPU nanofibers reached at least 96% in the third circle, and the recovery rate of the PZT 80%-M reached 84.8% in first cycle.

The output voltages of the piezoelectric materials increased at first as acceleration was increased. The 80% (wt%) PZT nanofibers produced voltages of 70.2 mV (peak-to-peak) at an acceleration of 470 mm/s² and frequency of 1000 Hz.

The PZT/SMPU nanofibers exhibit good potential for energy harvesting. The flexible SMPU matrices and electrospinning technology endowed the nanofibers with superior flexibility.